

A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY ON IN-PRISON TREATMENT OF PERSONS DEPRIVED OF LIBERTY IN A PENAL COLONY WITHOUT WALLS

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Abstract: This case study aimed to understand the lived experiences of the Persons Deprived of Liberty of Iwahig Prison and Penal Farm in Puerto Princesa City. The study utilized a qualitative research design using multiple case study approach, with seven Persons Deprived of Liberty chosen through purposive sampling. Coding type of analysis was used as a data analysis tool. Results revealed, that the PDL were experiencing just and humane treatment from the jail officers especially that they were provided meaningful and useful activities and programs. On the challenges and coping mechanisms, they mentioned that challenges are triggered by different factors and their coping mechanisms are varied and it is important for their survival inside the correctional facility. Further, their insights were shared by giving lessons they discovered through individual liberty deprivation. The lived experiences of the PDL are eye opener to the whole community, to support them in order to provide them a social service intervention meant to address the issues and difficulties encountered by the PDL, this support will bring great impact as it will transform the lives of the PDL.

Keywords: In-prison treatment, Persons deprived of liberty, transformation, case study, Puerto Princesa City, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Even the most physically and emotionally healthy individual experiences distress when they are in prison. The most distressing aspect of serving time in Philippine jails, though, is the severe congestion of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs). Thousands of prisoners were vying for a little space in jails, much beyond the capacity of these detention centers (Alipoyo, 2022). Life in jails and penitentiaries is likewise brutalized by overpopulation. Herding people into small quarters is an unsafe, demeaning, and a discriminatory kind of punishment. Overcrowding poses a threat to both human life and health. It spreads illnesses, undermines authority, and heightens conflicts.

This research can contribute to the realization of Item Number 16 (Peace Justice and Strong Institutions) of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations as adapted by the Philippine government. Every country's penal justice system constitutes prisons as a fundamentally important component. By ensuring that accused Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are held accountable and by penalizing severe malfeasance, it can be used to maintain the peace and order in a society. Hence, when a state takes away someone's freedom, it has a responsibility to make sure that person's dignity is protected. Countries must also guarantee the security and safety of prisons for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs), administrators,

guests, and the broader public. These two responsibilities are more complementary rather than in opposition to one another since security is best provided in a well-organized system that treats Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) fairly and humanely. At their finest, correctional facilities should still be able to provide Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) with a humane environment and possibilities for support and rehabilitation. At its worst, however, jails can be places of horrifying torment, breeding grounds for illness, or ineffective holding facilities from which Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are poorly prepared to live law-abiding lives once they are released.

There are seven (7) penal facilities in the Philippines, one was located in the province of Palawan the Iwahig Prison and Penal farm. The Bureau of Corrections supervises and manages Prison and Penal Farms where rehabilitation programs like livelihood projects, educational and vocational courses, recreational and athletic events, and religious/spiritual activities are organized. These programs are designed to provide Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) resources that will assist in their successful reintegration into society after release. Therefore, understanding the human being completely is fundamental to how Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) should be treated in prison. Particularly, one must recognize the concept of human dignity, which is inalienable and ought to be honored in every individual. This implies that criminals get the same respect as people with clean records, regardless of the crime they committed.

Since detention has been used as a punishment for crime, significant advancements have been made to improve prison conditions. The development of criminal justice reform in national legal systems is driven mostly by concerns about how PDLs are treated. There are several philosophical foundations that guide how Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are treated in prisons and other detention facilities around the world. Within the context of correctional management, four principles or philosophies of punishment are highly suggested. These include retribution, deterrence, incapacitation, and treatment (Gul, 2018).

While incapacitation and retribution are more concerned with the crime committed, treatment and deterrence are more focused on the offender. Retribution principles are widely criticized because most nations follow a predetermined penalty, which often results in a number of critical elements not being adequately taken into account (Lewis 2022; Apel and Diller, 2017). Deterrence frequently contradicts retribution because it views punishment as a security risk intended to stop criminal behavior in the future.

Incapacitation, like deterrence, aims to stop offenders from committing a crime in the future, but is typically done by physical methods. For instance, chopping off a robber's hand, which not only renders the culprit helpless but also discourages others from doing the same crime (Lewis 2022; Apel and Diller, 2017). Rehabilitation, in contrary to the first three principles, aims to reintegrate Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) into productive lives. Its objective is to reduce criminal recidivism and prevent repetitive offenses (Lewis 2022; Apel and Diller, 2017).

Also, historical records reveal that Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) were subjected to severe punishment and pitiful situations, including being left naked and chained. In the past, physical abuse was also a common occurrence. Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) with mental illnesses were also housed in the general community without access to therapy (Rubin, 2019). However, a series of protests and mass demonstrations resulted in the adoption of the United Nations Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners in 1955, which improved the conditions for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) and in correctional facilities (Rubin, 2019; UNODC, 1955).

Almost everybody agrees that the prime purpose of detention, whether it be in jails, juvenile detention centers, or other types of prison systems, is rehabilitation. Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are a complex, high-risk population (Day, 2020). Additionally, many prisoners are already in crisis as a result of their imprisonment. They deal with a variety of issues while they are detained and after they are released, including the stigma attached to having a criminal record, a lack access to social services such as housing, work opportunities, and access to education, as well as strained relationships with their families and other social welfare systems (Arbour et al., 2021).

Numerous studies have documented the lived experiences of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) as well as the policies and initiatives that have been established in order promote their well-being. The specific conditions of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)' infrastructure, services, health, and other opportunities have, however, received relatively insufficient investigation (Kahambing, 2021).

It is therefore necessary for policymakers and other relevant stakeholders understand how in-prison treatment can be successfully conducted inside a correctional system. The Iwahig Prison and Penal Farm will be the central focus of this dissertation's analysis of how Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) receive treatment while they are being detained and the

factors that influence that treatment. This dissertation emphasizes the importance of the developing specific policy interventions, strategies, and programs that take into account the myriad needs of PDLs and elevate inmate rehabilitation to the social position of a criminal justice priority rather than an adjuvant to the country's conventional justice system.

Numerous studies have repeatedly focused on the intricacy of how Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are treated in prison. Years of research have gone into figuring out the fundamentals of efficient inmate intervention programs. According to several theories and studies, prison time is a useful and essential strategy for ensuring safety in societies.

Despite the fact that theories of punishment and social defense provide useful solutions to the growing concern of reinforcing public order among countries, these theories lack the objectivity required for prioritizing initiatives and lack confidence in the efficacy of a number of these desired outcomes, making it difficult for correctional facilities to implement relevant programs, influenced by the fact that these principles are antithetical (Jouet, 2021).

Therefore, compared to how Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are treated within prison in the earlier times, several theorists of criminal justice suggest that rehabilitation is a much preferable course of action. A better prison atmosphere and the inclusion of positive external influences can aid in the reformation of the criminals' existing subcultural values. This demonstrates that restorative community-based and treatment-focused services within the penitentiary system may be the ideal method for reducing crime rates in societies (Bazemore, 1998). Morris's (2000) transformational justice theory, addressing the economic and social inequalities that lead to crime is fundamental to improving the overall quality of life for victims, Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs), and the society as a whole.

However, this idea promotes the deinstitutionalization of criminal justice by granting people and communities more authority. It presents the argument that all forms of violence, including those permitted by the government, need to end (Morris, 2000). Furthermore, advocates of this theory argue that all forms of state punishment and retribution should be discontinued, including the death penalty, torture, and the establishment of jails. Proponents of the transformative justice theory also advocate for social and governmental initiatives based on responsibility, forgiveness, inclusivity, and reconciliation (AVP, 2005; Morris, 2000).

The risk-need-responsivity (RNR) model, which was first created by Bonta and Andrews (1990), is now universally accepted as the best model for determining how to rehabilitate Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs). It asserts that an inmate's risk and needs should be adequately taken into account in designing interventions to manage his delinquent behavior, both before and after release (Jouet, 2021). The RNR model also describes the fundamental ideas of risk, needs, and responsivity to establish effective programs and interventions for inmate populations with the primary objective of rehabilitation and eventually, reintegration into society. The three significant aspects of the RNR paradigm are risk, need, and responsivity. The presence and probability of harmful circumstances are referred to as risks. Its two main components are the existence of potentially dangerous agents and the likelihood that the threats caused by these elements would materialize (Bonta, 1997; Bonta & Andrews, 2007).

The premise of risk is founded on values, and risk analysis is based on people's perceptions of the potential harm from an event and its probability of occurring. Consequently, determining a person's potential for harming himself or others is a component in the risk assessment process used in criminal justice. The assumption that the risk factors are separate and individualized is one that the RNR's proponents focus on (Ward & Durrant, 2021).

Therefore, the risk variables increase the probability that someone may act antagonistically or cause serious harm. Risk factors can be divided into four categories: dispositional, historical, contextual, and clinical (Ward & Durrant, 2021). Dispositional factors include cognitive qualities, antisocial or psychopathic personality behaviors, and demographic information. A negative psychiatric history, a criminal history, a history of sickness, and poor treatment compliance are examples of historical variables. Recidivism (risk factors for criminal activity), atypical social interactions, and an absence of supportive social networks are context-dependent variables. History of psychotherapy and medical records are examples of clinical factors (Herzog-Evans, 2017).

Risk and need are interrelated concepts. According to the RNR model, people whose needs are not addressed may pose a danger of harm. As a result, an unmet need can cause some harm (Bonta, 1997; Bonta & Andrews, 2007). In his hierarchy of needs, Maslow (1943) identified the following as the needs of an individual that must be met or satisfied: physiological needs, safety needs, social needs, and esteem needs. According to Maslow, satisfying all of these deficient needs is necessary for continuous growth and development, and doing so has a significant influence on how people behave (Maslow, 1970). After these inadequate requirements are met, humans can pursue higher-level "being needs" like self-actualization, in

accordance with Maslow's theory. The aspects of psychological fulfillment and well-being are included in human needs, and individuals can only grow if these needs are met (Maslow, 1968).

Although few of these weaknesses are linked to criminal behavior, the RNR model's proponents assert that these needs can be characterized as personal deficits (Hilton & Radatz, 2017). Criminally and non-criminally motivated needs are both referred to as needs. Criminogenic needs are pro-offending individual factors like impulsivity, lack of problem-solving capabilities, substance abuse issues, extreme animosity, and criminal affiliations. These are contrasted with non-criminogenic requirements, which refer to the characteristics of an individual or their environment that, if modified, may not directly affect recidivism rates, according to the RNR model (Hilton & Radatz, 2017; Viglione, 2018).

The process in which an offender responds to social interactions is referred to as "responsivity." This is influenced by the individual's willingness to engage in prison rehabilitation programs and commit to change. According to the responsivity principle, inmate activities should be adapted to their learning preferences, levels of motivation, and personal needs. As a result, the range of programs available to Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) must be able to effect the desired changes that are in accordance with the inmate's preferred methods of learning (Bonta, 1997; Bonta & Andrews, 2007).

Although the RNR model is frequently used as the benchmark for assessing Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) and determining how they should be treated, several researchers and professionals in the field of criminal justice contend that it lacks conceptual depth and theoretical underpinning (Ramezani et al., 2022). However, the model's proponents disputed this, asserting that it is based on three (3) theoretical frameworks: Psychology of Criminal Conduct perspective (Andrews, 1980), General Personality and Social Psychological Perspective on Criminal Conduct (Andrews & Bonta, 2010), and Personal Interpersonal Community-Reinforcement Perspective (Gillis, 2005).

The first stage or aspect of the RNR rehabilitation model consists of several basic considerations. First, reducing the harm that offenders cause to society and to the general public is the prime objective of rehabilitation programs for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) (Bonta, 1997; Bonta & Andrews, 2007). Second, there can be variations in each individual's inclination to commit crimes. Criminal behavior is influenced by a diverse range of factors, including contextual, psychological, social, cultural, cognitive, and physical factors (Taxman et al., 2018). Third, it is believed that the risk level varies with the degree of criminogenic needs as well as the strength or complexity of each. Fourth, the most important treatment priorities are those characteristics that research suggests may be associated with lower recidivism rates (Andrews et al., 2011).

The primary issue is that it is equally important to make the maximum use of the limited resources at hand to regulate criminality, which includes minimizing the situations that academic data has shown to trigger offenders (Tafrate et al., 2019). A risk-management rehabilitation approach prioritizes lowering the probability that people will act in ways that are detrimental to the society. Fifth, it is claimed that identifying risk factors and/or criminogenic needs is an empirical method necessary in the process (Herzog-Evans, 2017). Sixth, individuals should be treated with respect while in detention centers that uphold moral principles. Due to attributes like responsibility and motivation, as well as respect to fundamental human rights, Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) should be seen as sentient persons with the ability to commit crimes (Wormith & Zidenberg, 2018; Dyck et al., 2018).

As to the standard penal discipline, Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) should be fitted with programs based on assessments of their vulnerability, needs, and responsiveness. RNR embodies the who, what, and how of inmate intervention strategies. In terms of risk assessment, the RNR model has a demonstrated track record of directing realistically relevant risk instruments by leveraging on empirical knowledge of the variables linked to possible crime and scientific data of the trends that motivate decreases in recidivism after programs.

The greatest of aspirations and the most egregious of injustices can both be found throughout the existence of imprisonment. Cargo enslavement, deportation, jails, penitentiaries, and correctional institutions are a few examples of penal structures and mechanisms that were developed in part to relieve urban streets of the undesirables—both impoverished and criminal—or at the slightest to manage and control them. Therefore, to prevent the adoption of more violent or aggressive responses to such people, jails and community correctional programs were also established.

A number of significant principles that apply to prisoners are outlined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR). The rights to life, liberty, and personal security (Article 3), as well as the prohibition against torture and other degrading or inhumane methods of punishment (Article 5) are among them (United Nations, 2015b). Consequently, the Nelson Mandela Rules, also known as the UN's Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners (SMRs), are widely

regarded as the mandatory requirement for the treatment of PDLs and serve as a framework for what are generally considered as sound practices and standards in the management of jail institutions (United Nations, 2015a).

However, a substantial percentage of correctional institutions worldwide are going through a period of upheaval, which has substantial negative repercussions on Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs), their relatives, and society (Abbott et al., 2018). Meanwhile, the situation in many prison frequently falls short of international regulations and even threatens to undermine the main goal of a jail sentence: the defense of community against crime. Instead, there are numerous challenges that affect prison around the world. Overpopulation is a result of the world's correctional systems' ongoing growth in incarceration rates (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2017). It indicates that there are more Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) than the facility can accommodate legally.

Since more individuals are being sent to prison and for prolonged terms of imprisonment than the prisons can accommodate, there is overcrowding. Either exploitation of incarceration or inadequate prison facilities are the immediate causes of overcrowding. As a result, it leads to poor and inhumane conditions that spill over into other organizational and societal problems (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2017). Prison overcrowding, notwithstanding geographical differences, has become a serious global issue and is a significant barrier to the application of the Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners. As a result of this, prisons have the potential of becoming unsafe environments for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) and prison officials, as well as "crime schools" and attractive settings for radicalization, when penal systems are overburdened and poorly maintained (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2017).

The prevalence of infectious and chronic diseases, psychological problems, drug and alcohol abuse, brutality, self-harm, and death is exacerbated in overcrowded jails (Jacobson et al., 2017). Thus, the maintenance of prisoner wellness and the provision of a safe environment are challenging and common concerns caused by overcrowded prison all over the globe. Prisons that are overcrowded might have unsanitary, violent surroundings that are detrimental for

Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)' physical and psychological well-being (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2017).

In addition to this, the degree of overcrowding among prison is still very severe. More than 10.35 million people are detained in prisons and jails around the world, primarily as pre-trial Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs), detention prisoners, or convicted criminals (MacDonald, 2018). With 27 countries running at 150% to 200% capacity, overcrowding in prisons remains one of the most significant challenges in 2018. (Baggio et al., 2020).

In response to these concerns, building more prisons or implementing policy reforms like amnesties and early release programs to lower the number of convicts are the basically two approaches to debates about the detrimental effects of prison overcrowding. However, none of these solutions are effective in permanently lowering the number of PDLs (MacDonald, 2018). A crucial step in effectively combating the issues and worries for the welfare of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) and staff brought on by being incarcerated and working in overcrowded prison is the prevention of congestion. These preventative actions may include offering treatment for drug addiction programs, as well as enhancing educational and occupational opportunities (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2017).

The recommendations made by the UNODC in 2013 to lessen overcrowded prisons are largely similar and request for criminal justice system enhancements to achieve higher performance, create fair and equitable sentencing guidelines, and advance through-care initiatives to boost social reintegration and minimize the "revolving door" effect (European Parliament, 2017).

Two out of every five jails in England and Wales are unsafe, and two out of three prisons have subpar facilities, according to an assessment of prison inspection reports for 118 institutions the said regions (Savage & Townsend, 2018). Between 2013 and 2018, there was an average 175.4% congestion and a 73.2% turnover rate in the Swiss pre-trial prison. This indicated that the jail was overcrowded since there were more Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) than the facilities that could accommodate (Baggio et al., 2020). In the same study, Baggio et al. (2020) observed that turnover and overcrowding both had a significant statistical impact on prison violence ($b = 0.001$, $p .001$). Higher incidence rates of violence were linked to increased congestion and turnover.

Prison violence increased by 0.1 percentage points for every one point rise in prison overpopulation (on a scale of 100%) was observed by Baggio et al. (2020). This latest research emphasizes that institutional jail conditions may have significant negative consequences on incarceration and reintegration (Baggio et al., 2020). Additionally, for especially vulnerable

individuals living in confinement (such as those in poor health or with serious psychiatric conditions, and elder people), these negative impacts may be even more severe (Glazener & Nakamura, 2018).

The criminal justice system has reduced personnel and resources for prisons over the last three decades. Due to this, the prison system is now overburdened and unable to maintain the safety and decency norms demanded by international laws and regulations (MacDonald, 2018). Prison expenditures extend beyond the cost of the facilities and equipment. The institution that surrounds each individual, as well as the expenses of incarceration on their family members and children, have both social and psychological effects.

Additionally, although the "business" of prisons may assist the communities where they are situated, they are not always a desirable or appealing presence in neighborhoods (Gluckman, 2018). It is essential to consider about whether these incredibly high costs are effective in terms of improving victims' recovery, maintaining community safety, lowering crime and recidivism, and removing people from the "prison pipeline" (Jacobson et al., 2017). Programs for early intervention are unquestionably more cost-effective due to the high costs of criminality. Therefore, early preventive programs have been successful in significantly lowering long-term criminal justice spending. Early preventative investment is more economical than incarceration. The most cost-effective programs are those that target the individuals at the greatest risk, especially when they start earlier in the life cycle (Gluckman, 2018).

Evidence from other nations that have been successful in reducing their prison overcrowding, the criminal justice system should focus less on punishment but rather on rehabilitative treatment and reintegration. This should be done by increasing the alternatives for rehabilitation programs, such as intensive community supervision (Van Camp, 2017). The body of evidence needed for treatments inside and outside of the correctional system will often be produced through in-depth analyses of global criminal justice systems and an examination of pertinent policies and laws (Visher et al., 2017). In order for criminal justice reform to be successful and long-lasting, efforts should not be restricted to prison management and correctional institutions (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2017). Additional participation and recommendations from lawmakers, administrators, and criminal justice professionals from the authorities, prosecution, legal aid organizations, judges, and court systems may also be included.

On the other side, Southeast Asian prisons are typically extremely congested with Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) who must work, eat, and sleep in severely confined spaces. Prisons in Myanmar are notoriously out-of-date, overcrowded, and incapable of providing enough space and privacy (World Prison Brief, 2018; Human Rights Watch, 2020). With an occupancy rate of more than 400%, the Philippines currently has one of the most overcrowded jail systems in the world (Statista, 2021). Although challenging, reducing jail overpopulation ought to be a top priority. One of the most difficult issues facing Asian criminal justice systems, particularly in the Southeast Asian region, is the dramatic increase of the inmate population (Jefferson & Jeffries, 2022).

Southeast Asia's growing prison population is caused by a variety of factors that differ from each country. The size of those population densities is influenced by a variety of factors including social and economic policies, the presence or absence of social community resources and healthcare insurance services available in the community, crime prevention programs, the evolution of the criminal justice system, societal perceptions of violence, and the role of incarceration in combating crime (Jefferson & Jeffries, 2022). Other elements, such as a disproportionate use of prisons, mismanagement, punitive social programs, and rising income disparity, can also significantly affect the number of people imprisoned (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, 2017).

The effectiveness of the correctional facilities to provide convicts' basic healthcare, nutritional, and housing needs in addition to providing rehabilitation programs, education, training, and recreational opportunities is compromised by overcrowding in prisons, which also jeopardizes the welfare of prison staff and the general population (Jefferson & Jeffries, 2022).

In addition to making it difficult for correctional facilities to efficiently manage their resources, attend to Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)' demands for reintegration into society, and make sure that their rehabilitation complies with UN standards and guidelines, overcrowding can also put corrections officers in danger on the job. Additionally, it might prevent a reliable survey and efficient prisoner categorization (Jacobson et al., 2017). Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) who have limited access to rehabilitation programs are more likely to commit crimes again after being released. The inability of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) to reintegrate into the societal structure has a significant cost, both monetarily and in terms of public security (Day, 2020).

On the other hand, correctional facilities in Southeast Asia are also cautious about Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) becoming radicalized. To prohibit radicalization and the establishment and integration of terrorist groups inside facilities, the Indonesian government created the administration of high-risk prisons for terrorists in 2017. (Maulana et al., 2022). Another issue is that former prisoners who rejoin terrorist groups or networks as a result of poor intervention methods (Sumpter et al., 2019). Additionally, with a prison overcrowding proportion of 188%, the current state of affairs puts Indonesia in a vulnerable situation. This leads to a number of concerns, including inmate escapes, violence, organized narcotics trafficking inside jails, inmate-started prison fires, illegal payments made by prison guards, and other problems. These issues are brought on by a number of things, including the failure of correctional officers to follow prison guidelines correctly, a scarcity of resources and infrastructure, and an inefficient jail system (Utami Larasati et al., 2022).

Another major issue with Indonesia's penal system is the fact that there are less institutions and training courses accessible for female Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) than for male Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in the same regions (Institute for Policy Analysis of Conflict, 2020). The majority of these female Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) continue to reside in facilities that also house men. As a result, only sections or cell blocks separate the majority of Indonesia's female convicts from their male counterparts in detention facilities and correctional facilities (Wiryawan, 2019).

The same issues that affect its neighboring countries also plague Thailand's prison systems. The most urgent problem in Thai jails is still overpopulation and congestion. Thailand has the unfortunate reputation of having the most inmate population and the highest incarceration rate among the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) member nations. The country's inmate population has continuously expanded over the years (Jeffries et al., 2018). These correctional facilities are operating with an incarcerated population that is more than double the original capacity, with an occupancy level of 224%, according to the most recent official statistics, which constitute 91% of the total inmate population in the country (Bing & Albano, 2017).

On the other hand, Thai jails are still plagued by inadequate access to healthcare and other basic medical services, an insufficient supply of food and water, and poor sanitation facilities. Pregnant women are also in more need of medical treatment and special facilities to address their concerns (Chokprajakchat & Techagaisiyavanit, 2019). Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are frequently exposed to abusive treatment inside the facilities, which include unfavorable workplace environment and inadequate compensation. International conventions are breached by jail punishments, which can occasionally constitute torture and other forms of maltreatment (Jeffries et al., 2018).

On the other hand, it has been noted that the preponderance of the population in Singapore complies with the law. With multiple societal changes, including the adoption of new technology in the supervision of convicts and programs designed to prepare them for their reintegration into society, correctional facilities in Singapore have made significant progress over the past 20 years (Keung, 2017).

The Risk-Needs-and-Responsivity (RNR) Model, a widely used framework for the assessment and rehabilitation of delinquents, serves as the foundation for Singapore's strategy (Keung, 2017). Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are evaluated upon admittance to identify their needs for rehabilitation and likelihood of committing crimes. Appropriate programs are planned for intervention based on their assessed risks and needs. The programs include family services, skill-building courses, and religious activities. Penitentiary programs based on psychological principles are also included. Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) will also participate in various programs before their release that will get them equipped for community reintegration and development (Wormith & Truswell, 2022).

Singapore conducts regular program assessments and evaluations to make sure its approaches to rehabilitation is still appropriate and effective. Assessment studies showed that a particular category of offenders who underwent comprehensive rehabilitation programs had lower two-year rates of recidivism than those who did not. Moreover, these prisoners shown improvements in psychological and social functioning, a decline in criminal behaviors, a reduction in belief systems that supported substance abuse, and a higher likelihood of successfully reintegrating into society (Singapore Prison Service, 2022).

The Philippine setting is no different from other Asian correctional systems. The world's overcrowded penitentiary system is situated in the Philippines. The correctional facilities and penal institutions run by the Bureau of Corrections (BuCor) have an average overcrowding rate of about 500% compared to the correctional facilities run by the National Police, the jail facilities supervised by the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology and the provincial governments, and the detention facilities (Jones & Narag, 2019). Therefore, Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are compelled to compete for access to the most basic necessities, using bribery and other legal loopholes as a last option.

The percentage of women in correctional facility in the Philippines ranges from 2 to 9 percent. However, the number of women imprisoned is rising more quickly than the number of men (Alvarez, 2018). Due to the geographical location of women's prisons, women may experience fewer face-to-face interactions with their family members, mental health problems resulting from previous abuse and trauma, exposure to sexual violence by staff and other Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs), needs for reproductive health care, and the situations of having to separate from their children despite being their primary caregivers of you (Nieva, 2021).

Additionally, the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)' grievances about their health are also increasing as a consequence of overcrowding in correctional facilities. Since the Philippines "has the highest jail occupancy in the world," it is extremely difficult and possibly psychologically risky to evaluate this issue (Nieva, 2021). The HIV prevalence in the Philippines is already among the fastest-growing around the world, and the prevalence of HIV among Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) has been expanding across all penal institutions (Yarcia, 2018).

The rising HIV/AIDS outbreak in prisons has recently brought unprotected sexual intercourse between Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) to light. Unprotected same-sex activities among prison Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) along the complex spectrum from sexual activities to sexual assault have been commonly observed across regions of the world, despite varying incidence (Center for Gender Equality and Women's Rights, 2022). The following important issues, however, are not addressed in any explicit policies: the mitigation of rape and sexual assault; drug addiction rehabilitation, including opioid substitution medication and counseling services; and the prevention of HIV transmission through dental and medical treatment methods; prevention of HIV transmission from mother to child; treatment of sexually transmitted diseases; vaccination and treatment against viral hepatitis; in addition to tuberculosis prevention, diagnosis, and treatment (Yarcia & Bernadas, 2021)

Meanwhile, prison gangs are a common sight in Philippine correctional facilities. To protect themselves and to guarantee their survival, PDLs join pangkats or prison gangs. However, those who choose to stay unattached do so because they have a negative opinion of the pangkat, have access access to adequate social protection, and want to preserve their pre-prison identity (Lee & Narag, 2018). For the majority of prisoners, forming gangs is the realistic way to avoid exploitative Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) and violent prison staff. The gang leaders themselves, however, may abuse Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) once they are inside the groups (Narag & Lee, 2017).

Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are explicitly forbidden by the existing jail management systems from participating in prison administration or governance. In wealthy nations where the government can offer sufficient resources, infrastructure, and staff, this is possible. However, in emerging economies like the Philippines, where incarceration facilities are underfunded and marked by widespread poverty and corruption, it is not applicable (Lee & Narag, 2018). In these situations, inmate leaders frequently work collaboratively with prison officers on prison governance.

Despite advancements, there are still certain problems with classification scheme for detention facilities in the Philippines. Particularly, decisions that govern accommodation, program, and work assignments at the organizational or internal department must be as well-organized and disciplined as those established at the broader system or external level (Alipoyo, 2022). Internal categorization decisions become more important when prison systems are more overcrowded. Making decisions on accommodation and other related services, particularly for prisoners serving extremely long prison terms, will become more challenging as the prison population increases (Alipoyo, 2022).

There is mounting evidence that, in some situations, imprisonment can benefit Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in reintegrating into society. However, it is still completely unknown how jail might result in successful recovery (Abbott et al., 2018). Although there is compelling evidence in this emerging literature that favorable jail circumstances may lower recidivism, it is still questionable which specific characteristics are actually beneficial. Rehabilitation initiatives that emphasize education, improving professional skills, or providing specific psychosocial counseling are frequently put out as potential explanations for these findings (Arbour et al., 2021).

Despite inconsistent results across various analyses, some studies have demonstrated the value of instructional, restorative, occupational, and work programs in prison facilities, as evidenced by higher post-release workforce participation, increased employability, improved decision-making skills, better cognitive performance, pro-social reasoning, and lower rates of recidivism (Edwards, 2021). According to research, there are three aspects of criminal justice settings that characterize the potential for rehabilitation of jail systems: (a) demonstrated inmate security; (b) support given by community corrections staff and Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs); and (c) the inmate's perception of the environment as supportive of therapeutic intervention (Day, 2020).

Therefore, from the perspective of the PDLs, a constructive prison environment is one that is encouraging, secure, and upholds possibilities for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)' individual development (Edwards, 2021). Consequently, the degree to which Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) feel safe has the capability to have a significant influence on the outcomes of rehabilitation services and programs.

Since offenders violate the law for a broad range of reasons, there are many distinctive kinds or qualities of recidivists. Assessment and treatment programs can help some individuals, particularly those who commit criminal acts as a result coming from external influences such financial hardships, social conditioning, ignorance, etc (Arbour et al., 2021). Appropriate therapeutic interventions and rehabilitation services should be used with the relevant categories of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in order to address the specific requirements of each individual. Typically, therapy initiatives performed in some countries are considered as initiatives enhancing offenders' socioeconomic capabilities, such as employment in jail, vocational training, and education (Arbour et al., 2021).

Each and every human being has the basic right to health free from any type of discrimination. It is the duty of the governments to ensure its citizens, including those who are detained, equitable access to healthcare and medical assistance and services (Chuenurah et al., 2021). Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) may develop a variety of illnesses, addictions, or other health problems due to their restricted access to high-quality healthcare and medical treatments, poor diet, potential substance abuse, and susceptibility to contagious diseases. Moreover, overcrowding in prison environments can result in inadequate medical treatment, a lack of manpower, poor personal hygiene practices, and unclean environments, all of which could worsen Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)' health (Yarcia & Bernadas, 2021).

Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs), especially those who were previously unable to access community health care facilities, may benefit from improved health care as a result of their confinement. Several of them may have their first experience for a thorough medical evaluation during the prison medical assessment, which includes the identification, prognosis, and treatment of psychological and/or physical health problems (Pont & Harding, 2019). There is a strong need to manage the complicated medical requirements of correctional facilities since diminishing healthcare disparities is a fundamental tenet of worldwide public health policy (Stürup-Toft et al., 2018). The concurrent and interrelated purposes of ensuring equitable care and promoting health are thus obligatory for a correctional facility, which provides a chance to enhance the health of marginalized populations (Macleod et al., 2020).

When compared to regular Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs), sexual harassment among sexual and gender minority convicts in jails and correctional facilities occurs at incredibly high rates (Donohue et al., 2021). The prejudice, exclusion, and violence LGBT individuals encounter in society at large are frequently reflected and exacerbated in the correctional facility. Males who identify as gay or homosexual are 11 times more likely than heterosexual men to report being sexually molested by an inmate, while males who identify as bisexual are 10 times more likely. Lesbian and bisexual Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) reported increased rates of sexual abuse by prison staff, while bisexual Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are more likely to report sexual abuse by another inmate than heterosexual or lesbian Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) (The Fenway Institute, 2018). Prisoners who identify as transgender are especially at risk. According to New York inmate statements, the environment for transgender, gender nonconforming, and intersex Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) is particularly dangerous due to verbal harassment, physical violence, molestation, and coercion (Brown & Jenness, 2020).

Additionally, a disproportionate number of Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer (LGBTQ) individuals reside in prisons. When it comes to regulations, standards, and compliance, the prison environment is rigorous, constrictive, heterosexist, and overly macho for the LGBTQ+ people there (Donohue et al., 2021). Many of the medical requirements of LGBTQ+ persons are unrecognized and unfulfilled while they are imprisoned, which may have a catastrophic impact on their health and well-being (Brown & Jenness, 2020). Although there are encouraging initiatives to enhance the prison environment, there are still both personal and institutional impediments that make it difficult to be LGBTQ+ in jail (Brown & Jenness, 2020).

On the other hand, Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) frequently feel unprepared for release and reintegration. They find it difficult to reintegrate back into society. The obstacles of daily existence outside of prison are difficult to navigate with since there is inadequate human and social resources available and accessible to them (Andvig et al., 2020). Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) claimed that they were treated with humanity in the prison's social landscape, which was a significant positive factor, however, they are faced with difficulties upon release (Arbour et al., 2021). Mutual respect and trust between prisoners and prison staff appeared to increase their sense of fairness and equality. The social environment

served as a learning opportunity for establishing independence and individuality. Prisoners pick up teamwork, social skills, and social capital (Andvig et al., 2020).

The majority of offenders struggle with social reintegration challenges that can include stigmatization and exclusion from their families and communities. This makes it difficult for them to find employment or residence, go back to school, or develop and restore their personal and social capital. Without support to address these concerns, they run the danger of succumbing to a cycle of ineffective social integration, committing crimes, recidivism, and social ostracization. The successful social rehabilitation and reintegration of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) into society and their recovery should consequently be among the fundamental objectives of criminal justice systems.

To provide a clearer understanding of the contents of this paper, an operational definition of the terms used in this study is presented: Case Study is defined as the detailed and investigative analysis of the lived experiences of the individuals involved in the conduct of a research study. It provides a framework on how complex issues are evaluated and analyzed. It aims to generate a multi-faceted evaluation of complex issues among societies or across various situations; In-Prison refers to the type of confinement found in jails, where individuals are detained. It also refers to institutions where persons are confined as a form of punishment by a judicial authority while they await their trial or are sentenced to conviction. These institutions are usually operated by the state; Persons Deprived of Liberty refers to individuals who are confined in an institution or facility and detained in custody.

In this research study, this term refers to individuals who are jailed in lawful custody while undergoing trial or awaiting a lawful sentence; and lastly, Treatment is used in this study to refer to the practices, initiatives, and strategies used by jails to meet Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)' basic needs and provide services that protect their inherent dignity as humans. This phase is considered essential in the reintegration of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) to societies in the purpose of developing to become responsible citizens.

The treatment of prisoners in Western countries' correctional facilities has been the focus of numerous research studies. However, limited studies were published on the assessment of current jail situation trends in Asia, particularly among developing countries like the Philippines. A practical approach to reduce inequalities among prisons and optimize the management of correctional facilities in the Philippines is strongly recommended in the struggle to improve living conditions in these infrastructures. The research will focus on certain sub-themes on how Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are cared for through the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) Welfare and Development Programs, including livelihood programs, educational development, health care services, recreation, and spiritual activities. As a result, the results of this study can contribute in the formulation of relevant policy suggestions for the Prison and Penal Farm Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) Welfare and Development Program. Furthermore, a better understanding of society will be established through the analysis of the perspectives presented in this study, thereby paving the way for human development programs for PDLs.

This study investigated the lived experiences of selected Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in Iwahig Prison and Penal Farm using a qualitative-descriptive research design. The procedures for data collection approach are the most appropriate for the study since it explicitly analyzes how prison Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are treated inside of correctional facilities, how their grievances are addressed by the authorities, and what needs they have that should be met by the management.

Further, the research study is guided by the following research questions: How are PDLs treated at Iwahig Prison and Penal Farm?; How do PDLs cope with the challenges they have encountered in the correctional facility?; and What insights can they share to other PDLs and to the community as well?

Prison can be environments where violence proliferates, or they can be channels for reform. Prison sentence is the standard sentences for crimes, but part of the rehabilitation process requires finding a delicate balance between enforcing punishment and effectively addressing the reasons of criminal conduct.

Research on global incarceration rates has previously been reported in a large number of studies. Studies have been carried out on a global scale to identify and assess the existence of several jail types internationally as well as the social environments that these institutions provide for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs). Limited research, however, has concentrated on the circumstances of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)' daily everyday lives and their personal experiences. The results of this study will fill a gap in the studies on correctional facilities in Asia, especially among developing nations.

This study aims to investigate the experiences and perspectives of prison Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) on their treatment in Iwahig Prison and penal Farm. The findings are aimed at providing national government officials necessary data they can use to allocate resources for strengthening the management systems of the correctional facilities and jails, which will contribute to improve the social conditions of the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs).

By conducting this research, it will be possible to identify the best approaches and shed some light on the treatment of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in IPPF. These results can therefore influence policy changes and enhance living conditions and treatment interventions for Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs). The research can also be beneficial for the following: Iwahig Prison and Penal farm Management. The study will help the primary government agency in charge of supervising correctional facilities in the Philippines develop practical strategies and approaches for the rehabilitation of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs).

The study can also enable the BuCor to review and assess the programs and initiatives that are already in place using the direct experiences of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs); Social Workers. This study is expected to be helpful to social workers who provide assessment and intervention programs to prisoners. They provide treatment assessments for appropriate interventions, conduct individual counseling, plan group activities, and identify at-risk Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in order to enhance and support rehabilitation and reintegration. As such, the study will provide empirical evidence on how in-prison treatments are viewed by Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs); and to the Future Researchers, the findings reported in this study can be utilized as a reference for future research or to verify the validity of other studies. This research will also act as a cross-reference, providing future researchers with a background or understanding of the variables used for in-prison treatment of Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs).

The primary focus of this study was on real life experiences on how Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) are treated in Iwahig Prison and Penal Farm. The purpose of this research is to evaluate and assess the basic needs and other essential services that prison systems in the IPPF provide to Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs)— or the lack thereof.

2. METHOD

This chapter describes the several approaches that were taken in order to collect and analyze data that was pertinent to the study. The study's participants, research design, ethical consideration, and data gathering methods are only a few of the topics covered by the techniques.

Study Participants

Using a purposive sampling method, seven (7) PDL from Iwahig Prison and penal farm are selected for this study. This research study employs qualitative research using a multiple case study research design. The participants are selected using a non-probability sampling approach, more specifically the purposive sampling method. Case studies often focus on small samples and are designed to investigate a real-world experience rather than make statistical inferences about the general populace (Gill, 2020).

Although a sample of participants or cases needed not be random or representative, there were good reason to favor particular situations or people over others. In addition, this study employed coding type of analysis, in order to identify particular themes and concept to better understand the result of the study. Thus, coding is a qualitative data analysis strategy in which some aspect of the data is assigned a descriptive label that allows the researcher to identify related content across the data (Saldana, 2016).

For inclusion criteria, seven (7) Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) from the research locations participated in the study as participants. They were purposefully selected by considering regardless of their age but their capacity to interact/speak with people and psychographic characteristics based on their personality and their attitude towards others and how they behave inside the facility, with the help of the prison supervisor. The primary criteria in choosing participants in this research study are whether they have at least twelve (12) years of prison experience, are under minimal security supervision, and had demonstrated a good behavior as per their prison records inside the correctional facilities. Only willing PDL's are considered as the respondents of the study. In addition, respondents that are in medium and maximum security supervision are excluded from the study for security purposes since maximum security confines PDLs who commits heinous, although PDLs inside medium security poses lesser danger than maximum, yet they are more danger than PDLs in minimum security.

Moreover, those questionnaires that was not answered by the respondents are excluded. Further, those respondents who decided or wished to withdraw during the course of the study due to some reasons are let off.

The National Capital Region and other major cities in the country are the focus of much of the writing on prison and jail conditions. However, there has been minimal research done to evaluate prison and jail facilities among Philippine provinces. Additionally, MIMAROPA's booming economy is fueled by a multitude of relevant industries. The assessment of the facility in the province and how these facilities treat Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) can also determine how local governments prioritize and resolve issues and common grievances among prison management, or the absence of such response.

Materials and Instrument

The instrument used in the study is an interview guide. The instrument as validated by experts with an external validator. The expert summary rating and comments garnered an overall rating of 10 with a descriptive rating of very good. The interview guide were administered to the identified participants of the study.

An interview guide is a document that enables the researcher to structure the way she conduct their candidate interviews. It helps researcher to know what to ask about and in what order and it ensures a candidate experience that is the same for all participants.

Design and Procedure

In this study, the same dynamics were examined across the cases by use of a multiple case study method. This approach is selected so that individual case studies can (a) forecast findings that are literally replicated or (b) predict results that are different, but for the expected reasons (Yin, 2017).

The study utilized an interview guide with open-ended questions. The expertise of research experts will also be requested to properly validate it. The research instrument is organized into three subtopics: the first examines perceptions of how they are treated in Iwahig Prison and Penal Farm; the second examines the informants' examines the issues or difficulties they encountered while in custody; and the third examines their learned lesson in regards with their life-long experiences.

The permission to conduct this study will be secured from the Bureau of Corrections through the Superintendent of Iwahig prison and Penal Farm. The purposes of the study will be presented to the informants and the prison administrators prior to the conduct of this research. The informants will then be requested to sign a consent form affirming their willingness to participate in the research study. Furthermore, the informants will be informed that their identities will be kept private.

This study was approved by the University of Mindanao Ethics Review Committee with protocol number 2023-235. All ethical issues and concerns were taken into account when accomplishing the research. Informed consent was also signed to guarantee full permission for data collection. The participants were also informed by the researcher that their participation would be kept private and that the data collected would only be used for study. Their answers will be kept private to protect their welfare. The study's sources were accurately credited and paraphrased to provide information free of plagiarism. This is to recognize the supporters of the sources that this study used.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section is all about the result and discussion of the study. It specifically presents the descriptive tables outlining the answers of the themes on each qualitative questions and also presents the narratives for each theme supported by different literature from reliable sources. Thus, it specifically discusses the lived experiences of the Persons Deprived of Liberty (PDLs) in Iwahig Prison and Penal Farm (IPPF) including the challenges they have experienced, how they were treated inside IPPF, their coping mechanism as well as their realizations and lessons that they may share to the community. The main objective of this case study is to discover and investigate the lived experiences that lie behind the PDLs. Seven Person Deprived of Liberty from Iwahig Prison and Penal Farm participated in this study. Thus, they were coded as PDL1, PDL2, PDL3, PDL4, PDL5, PDL6 and PDL7 to maintain their confidentiality. This case study revealed evidences about the informant's experiences, challenges, coping mechanisms, how they treated as well as their lessons that they can share to the community.

Moreover, the objective of this study is to explicitly analyze how they were treated inside the correctional facility, how their grievances were addressed by the authorities and the needs that they have that should be met by the management. Additionally, its sole purpose was to delve even farther into the meat of the matter and bring to the fore the perspectives, thoughts, and emotions of the Person Deprived of Liberty.

Furthermore, the researcher made a table that shows the data classified and grouped to create major themes from the core ideas/ statements. Three main themes were yielded from the Person Deprived of Liberty concerning their experiences, these are their description of their experiences with the treatment of Bureau of Corrections, challenges and coping mechanisms, and insights or realizations.

Table 1. The Participants’ Description on their Lived Experiences inside the Correctional

Major Themes	Core Ideas/Statements
Experiences are varied and a case-to-case basis situation	Experiences inside the correctional is not easy but not hard enough Life inside the correctional is hard because of lack of family support Life inside the correctional is balanced Life inside the correctional is like normal community but guided by rules and regulations
Person Deprive of Liberty experienced Just and Humane Treatment	Person Deprived of Liberty were guided Properly by the jail officers Person Deprived of Liberty were treated fairly in the correctional Person Deprived of Liberty were treated with respect Person Deprived of Liberty were treated humane and just
Person Deprived of Liberty were provided by meaningful and useful activities and programs	Recreational Activities Livelihood Programs Spiritual Activities Educational Programs

Experiences are Varied and a Case-to-Case Basis Situation

It is just okay, since we are treated like normal people outside, however, we are guided by rules and regulations, like the there is a time for sleep, and we need to follow that (PDL1 Line 40-57).

Sometimes life here is happy but sometimes it is sad (PDL2 Line 510).

My life here inside also went well because it seems that if you were on the loose, like the life outside ma'am, you have many friends, troops, whatnot. Here you I experience the real camaraderie with others, you will also get along with the employees who can teach you the right thing (PDL 3 Line 925).

Life inside ma’am is a bit hard since we do not have support from our family (PDL 5 Line 1712-1717).

Our life here is okay, sometimes they were strict in management, sometimes loose. It is balanced (PDL 7 Line 2422-2426).

The first theme arose on the description of the participants with regards to their lived experiences as Person Deprived of Liberty is “Experiences are Varied and a Case-to-Case Basis Situation”, this shows that Person Deprived of Liberty have different views and descriptions on their life inside the correctional. It is revealed that their life inside was mostly described as a normal life since they were living as if they were a normal people living outside, however, participants added that they were bounded by rules and regulation wherein they need to follow it accordingly. Thus, some of the participants also mentioned that although life inside is easy, there are times that they experienced difficulties and sadness especially if they think of their family outside.

This result can be aligned to the study conducted by Gales et. al (2023) wherein the results of their in-depth analysis revealed that PDL who went through change faced difficulties and challenges inside the jail. Thus, it involves negative and positive experiences; negative because they experienced longing for their family and loneliness and positive because they experienced change inside the jail and learned from their mistakes in the past through the help and guidance by the rules and regulations imposed inside.

Person Deprived of Liberty description on their life experiences varies depending on how they view their life inside the correctional. It is based on their perception and coping mechanisms on how they handled the consequences they have as punishments for the crime they have committed. Moreover, they sounded optimistic as they view their life experiences

positively since they feel that they were living inside the correctional as a normal people although they limitations. In addition, they describe life inside positively as they have gained strong camaraderie among each other and that they were properly guided by the rules and regulations employed by the jail officers.

Further, PDL also mentioned that acceptance is their key to view experiences inside positively. However, along with these positive experiences are some negative experiences. PDL sometimes feel loneliness and hardships especially when they feel that have lack of support from their family.

Also based on the result, overall description of the PDL in their experiences may imply that their life inside is balanced since they are experiencing both positive and negative experiences. Thus, Pulangco et.al (2019) mentioned that the informal PDL social system is the primary inter-relational support system being operationalized by the PDLs to meet their basic needs and that the “brigada” is their highest social network and it plays an important role in the overall experiences of the PDL in the facility since it helps them build strong support for each other.

Person Deprive of Liberty experienced Just and Humane Treatment

Their treatment is humane (*PDL 1 Line 47*). How they treat us helps us in our daily life here inside, we have some sort of enjoyment when they tell us to do this and that. Aside from that, they will give us token (“*pang-kape*”) if they have want us to do side jobs for them (*PDL1 Line 230-250*).

The jail officers are treating us nicely, they are respecting us as normal people even if we are prisoners, like normal people who have worthy of respect (*PDL 3 Line 1107-1116*).

The jail officers are guiding us on what needs to be done inside the correctional especially during the brigade like cleaning. They always tell us to treat the correctional as our own house by taking care of it and to maintain its cleanliness. They are also nice, they are a good person (*PDL 4 Line 1344-1355*).

We were treated like we are a normal people, not prisoners (*PDL 7 Line 2434-2438*).

The second theme emerged on the description of the participants regarding their experiences inside the correctional is “*Person Deprived of Liberty Experienced Just and Humane Treatment*”, this means that the participants have experienced fair and just treatment inside the correctional facility. PDL were treated humanely and with respect, participants described clearly how they were respected and valued by the officers of the correctional. Person Deprived of Liberty were properly managed inside the correctional and they mentioned that it helped them in some way to cope up and adjust in their life inside.

This result was supported by the Commission on Human Rights (CHR) of the Philippines wherein it is stressed out that preserving the human rights and dignity of all persons, including PDLs, is a fundamental human rights guarantee.

Thus, the Republic of the Philippines has its obligations under the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the Optional Protocol to the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (OPCAT), and has since enacted Republic Act No. 9745 or “An Act Penalizing Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman, and Degrading Treatment or Punishment” in 2009 to clearly articulate the State’s policy of respecting the dignity and guaranteeing the rights of PDLs.

In addition, according to CHR the Republic of the Philippines is also following the UN Standard Minimum Rules for the Treatment of Prisoners, also known as Nelson Mandela Rules, further provides that the “safety and security of prisoners, staff, and service providers and visitors shall be ensured at all times” and that “[n]o prisoner shall be subjected to, all prisoners shall be protected from, torture and other cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment or punishment, for which no circumstances whatsoever may be invoked as a justification.” Moreover, to strengthen this, Senator Raffy Tulfo authored the Senate Bill 2031 also known as “Jails and Prisons Monitoring Act of 2023,” this bill reiterates the commitments of human rights commitments by the State improving transparency in jails and places of detention, it will also act as reinforcement to strengthen the accountability of duty-bearer in cases of human rights violations.

It can be seen in the result of the study that the PDL was protected by law and that the jail officers were strictly following it in order to protect and serve the PDL according to what is right and what is humane, this was also to make PDL safe and secure and at the same time, in order to make them feel valued and worthy of second chance despite crimes they have committed in their past.

Person Deprived of Liberty were Provided by Meaningful and Useful Activities and Programs

We have provided programs and activities here inside the correctional because every night we have prayer and devotions, we are also encouraged to attend holy mass, every Saturdays for the Adventist and every Sundays for Catholics and Born Again. There are priest/pastors who comes here and we are allowed to choose what religion we want to attend to. Aside from spiritual activities, we also have livelihood programs, we are creating handicrafts, in terms of handicrafts, it is like our projects wherein we can showcase our talent and creativity. Aside from this, we also have physical activities, we are allowed to join and choose what activities we want, such as basketball, table tennis, and tennis. These programs helped us, it helped us to condition our mind (PDL 3 Line 971-1024).

I joined electrical conducted by TESDA and martial arts. It good they have given us the opportunity to join in this kind of program, they taught us and they showed us how it is done and until today, it is still on my mind and I can use it someday if I would be given the chance get my freedom, I can use it outside (PDL 7 Line2447-2467).

The third theme emerged on the description of the participants in their description on their experiences in their life inside is “Person Deprived of Liberty were Provided by Meaningful and Useful Activities and Programs”. This means that the participants were experienced joining and engaging in the activities and programs provided by the Bureau of Corrections. According to the results, these experiences helped the PDL to have a meaningful experience inside the correctional. These programs helped them to become more physical and mentally active and at the same time it helped to develop their faith. Aside from these, the experiences gained and learned by the PDL with the said activities and programs helped them in their every living, it helped by means of having an extra income, conditioning their physique and mind and also strengthening their faith by letting them experience that there is Divine Being up there.

This notion was supported by Murcia (2022) wherein he stated that the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology were implementing educational and livelihood programs for the Persons Deprived of Liberty. It is furtherly mentioned that there is Jail-based ALS classes who were taught by BJMP staff who are certified educators familiar with the ALS instructional methods. He also mentioned that livelihood programs offered for the PDLs are income generating activities, so that they can sustain their needs inside and their family.

In addition, livelihood projects, including the making of paintings, bagmaking, bead products, baking, hair styling, cooking tutorials, pedicure and manicure, sewing, tailoring and weaving, masonry, mask making, rugmaking, carpentry, urban gardening, and diamond painting/rhinestone making, are popular livelihood projects among PDL. Moreover, Susbilla (2023), added that aside from this educational and livelihood programs, PDLs were also provided spiritual programs which is committed to providing PDLs a self-development and transformation before their eventual release and reintegration into society.

The results showed that the programs given to the PDLs are committed to provide a meaningful experiences and engagement that helps them grow and learn inside the correctional facility. These programs help them to transform and have a holistically self-improvement as their preparation for their release in the community outside the correctional.

Table 2. Participants’ Challenges and Coping Mechanisms

Major Themes	Core Ideas/Statements
Challenges are Triggered by Different Factors	Major problem is the scarcity in hygienic needs such as soap, toothpaste etc. Inadequate foods and water supply Frequent Power Interruptions Family Support and Assistance
Coping Mechanisms are Varied and Important for Survival	Enduring the situation in order to adapt and adjust Engaging in programs and activities provided by BuCor Spending leisure time or spare time to forget the life we have inside Faith in the Divine Being above

Challenges are Triggered by Different Factors

One of the problems here inside the correctional is the scarcity of personal hygiene specifically the bath soap (*PDL 1 Line 209-213*).

The hardest situation that I had experienced was getting sick while far away from my parents (*PDL 7 Line 2524-2525*).

Sometimes water supply, sometimes interruptions on water supply are caused by interruptions of power supply, it is too here (*PDL 3 1053-1054*).

The hardest situation I experienced was when I heard the news my father died and my wife re-married another man at the same time, it was really hard for me (*PDL 5 Line 1776-1778*).

One of the major problems of the PDLs, I think, sometimes when the soap runs out, it is really hard for us (*PDL 2 Line 718-722*).

Inadequate water and soap, it's not always the same, especially when it is brownout especially after the typhoon Odette, it is super-hot in the brigade (*PDL 3 Line 1032-1033*).

The problem that we always encounter is for our personal needs like hygienic soap (*PDL 6 Line 2129, Line 2157*).

Problems in our pocket, this is my main problem since we do not have money to buy our personal hygienic needs like colgate, at the same time our food like coffee, if we do not have money, we cannot buy our basic needs (*PDL 7 Line 2473-2482*).

The first theme arose for the challenges and coping mechanisms of the Persons Deprived of Liberty in their lived experiences inside the correctional is “*Challenges are Triggered by Different Factors*”, this means that informants who represented thousands of PDLs in Iwahig Prison and Penal Farm have something in common in terms the challenges that they have experienced inside the correctional, thus, informants stated that one of the major and common problems that the PDLs experienced and still experiencing inside the correctional is the inadequate supplies of their basic and personal needs such as food and personal hygienic needs especially their bath soap, inadequate food and water supply, frequent power interruptions and assistance and support from their family.

The result was supported by Chokprajakchat & Techagaisiyavanit (2019) to which they mentioned that the Thai jails are still plagued by inadequate access to healthcare and other basic medical services, an insufficient supply of food and water, and poor sanitation facilities. Hence, Gales et.al. (2023) addressed in their study that one of the major problems encountered by the inmates inside was insufficient supply food and personal hygiene kits since it was budgeted for thousands of inmates.

The findings demonstrated that even though the government met PDLs' basic needs, they still felt inadequate and insufficient because there were a large number of them inside. In addition, family issues have a significant impact on PDLs' lives, particularly if they believe they are receiving insufficient support and assistance. Learning tragic news from their relatives outside also has an impact on PDLs. The PDLs have indicated that these challenges impact them, primarily on a physical and emotional level. However, they have managed to overcome these challenges by using various strategies to modify and adjust.

Coping Mechanisms are Varied and Vital for Survival

I was wondering why this has to happen, but by the mercy of the Lord God, I also have accepted everything, ma'am (*PDL 5 Line 1800-1801*). When I pray at night, my mind seems to lighten, ma'am, even though it's heavy, it seems like someone is telling you that able to do it (*Line 1807-1808*). Our brotherhood in the church also helped me, they keep on telling me not to think of it so much and just say my prayers to the Lord (*Line 1822-1823*).

I have adjusted and cope up with my life inside through the help of the BuCO community, they provided for the things I needed in my painting since painting helped me to enjoy my spare time and it helped me condition my mind every time I have hard times here inside (*PDL 5 Line 1848-1849*).

I have to endure the challenges inside especially when times I cannot buy my personal needs since I do not have the financial capacity (*PDL 7 Line 2516-2517*).

I have adjusted and cope up here through engaging in the programs of BuCor, I personally joined martial arts, I also make my own dumbbells for exercising. Practicing my dumbbells really helped me to adjust here and I also follow what they are teaching us so that I can continue my life and I don't really think of my situation here, I just my mind that this is my life now (PDL 7 Line 2640- 2644, Line 2662-2665).

The second theme emerged from the description of the participants in their challenges and coping mechanism inside the correctional facility is, "Coping Mechanisms are varied and Important for Survival", this theme emerged since most of the informants have mentioned variety of coping mechanism in order to cope up adjust on their life inside. Coping mechanism are varied depending on how the PDLs handle their experiences and life inside. Thus, it can be seen in the results that most of them are engaging on programs and activities offered by Bureau of Corrections, strengthening their faith in the Divine Being, enduring and accepting their life inside as coping mechanism in order to survive.

This notion was supported by Barolo & Vicente (2019) to which they stated that difficulties in adjusting in prison life have effects on the life of the Persons Deprived of Liberty, thus, the effects of these difficulties vary among individuals because they have their own ways of adapting to the prison environment. Moreover, some PDLs would have thought of self-destruction, while majority developed adaptive behavior towards incarceration. Other repercussions of challenges are self-reflection and self-renewal, faith in God, prison as a haven and positive outlooks in life. Coping up with the prison environment the PDLs chose to become submissive, bear the consequences of their act, keeps themselves busy, and, remained active in religious activities.

Furthermore, because they have endured these experiences in order to survive, Persons Deprived of Liberty have unique perspectives on how they manage and adapt to the surroundings inside the correctional facility. It is beneficial that they have their own internal community, which has not only helped them cope but also heal and grow from the mistakes they have made in the past. It's encouraging to learn that PDLs are receiving excellent support and guidance from the Bureau of Corrections as a whole, which will help them adjust to life inside.

Table 3. Participants' Insights as Person Deprived of Liberty

Major Themes	Core Ideas/Statements
Lessons Discovered through Individual Liberty Deprivation	Respect for each other's life Thinking multiple times before doing wrong things Discipline is the key for righteous life Being hot tempered will not bring good to your life

Lessons Discovered through Individual Liberty Deprivation

First, respect and then be courteous in that way you will have good thoughts in your mind (PDL 2 Line 844-848).

My advice is that, I hope that they (co-PDLs) will always do the right thing so that if they will be given a chance to finally get back their freedom, their lives will be better. And for the people outside this community, also think carefully before they anything that will cause other people harm, in that way, they will not end up like us (PDL 2 Line 862-877).

To my co-PDLs here inside, always have discipline, learn to have discipline and that always follow on the rules and regulations, so that they will not get into trouble even if it is against their will, there is nothing wrong in following the rules. (PDL 1 405-419).

The lesson that I may share is to humble ones' self and to respect other people and also, to pray and seek for the Lord's guidance and put the Lord in your heart and (PDL 3 Line 1232-1238). And to the people outside this community, do not be hot tempered, do not engage on evil deeds (Line 1256).

The first theme emerged on the participants' insights as Person Deprived of Liberty is, "Lessons Discovered through Individual Liberty Deprivation", theme talks about the lessons that the Persons Deprived of Liberty have learned based on their lived experiences inside the correctional facility. Results showed that the major lesson that they have learned and wanted to share to their co-PDLs and to the people outside the correctional facility to be mindful before doing actions that they regret later on in life. Aside from this, they also learned about respect and discipline and they wanted to tell everyone how it changed their life and perspectives. Further, they also wanted to share that asking for the Lord's guidance in everything that an individual do will help them in doing righteous things.

This concept was supported by Santos (2022) wherein he stated that during his interviews on inmates, they have mentioned that prior to entering prison, their priorities and thinking were out of order, their selfish wants stood above everything else and none of the things they do was aligned with their values. However, on prison, they have learned and practices restructuring their priorities based on moral compass and goals for personal growth and learned that being in a confined area with so many different people around allowed them to see their choices in actions and that they realized and recognized that their actions spoke louder than words, that is why they practiced doing right thing every day even when nobody is watching them.

Implication for Practice

The public is greatly impacted by the personal experiences of those who are Deprived of Liberty. Their combined experiences have opened our eyes to both great and negative aspects of the Bureau of Corrections, their family, and the community. Their experiences living inside the prison have a significant impact on their personal development. This research lauded the Bureau of Corrections' Jail Officers for their excellent supervision and fair and compassionate treatment of PDLs. Nonetheless, it is advised that the government, working with the Bureau of Corrections, provide answers to the issues raised by this study, particularly those pertaining to the PDLs' access to basic necessities and personal needs, such as food, water, a comfortable place to live, and sanitary supplies.

Furthermore, it is advised that PDLs' families make more visits and offer their support to the members of their family who are incarcerated. They will feel less of the weight they are carrying inside of them, which will inspire and push them to work hard and hold out hope that they may one day be released from prison.

The study may also present a way for the Bureau of Corrections to hire additional professional counselors, increasing the number of outlets available to PDLs for sharing and releasing internal burdens, particularly those related to emotional and mental health issues. This may also seek help to the public to visit more and support the Iwahig Prison and Penal Farm so that they can generate more income for the benefit of the PDLs.

Because they stand to benefit from the research, the Bureau of Corrections may also choose to use the study's findings to inform the development of social service interventions meant to address the issues and difficulties raised during the interview.

Implication for Future Research

In my capacity as a researcher, I hope that the findings of this study will inspire other researchers to carry out similar research and carry on developing a program that will help those who are denied of their freedom. Future scholars may also carry out investigations connected to the current research and broaden their comprehension of the daily experiences of Persons Deprived of Liberty.

Concluding Remark

Similar to other types of confinement, being imprisoned causes a person a great deal of stress. Even though people may adjust and cope with life, situations like these have the power to alter a person's biophysical balance to the point where the recollection of a specific traumatic incident overwhelms all other experiences and impairs one's capacity to deal with reality. Thus, there are various factors that influence how inmates adjust to life behind bars. These include their personality, specifically their hope and optimism dispositional position; their ability to create a routine that gives their lives meaning and purpose; their ability to comply with prison rules while maintaining a sense of autonomy and control over their lives; the level of family contact they have; and the opportunities they have to pursue employment and education once they are freed from the life they have right now.

Deprived individuals are human beings who should be given another chance. The Persons Deprived of Liberty can gain more positive insights and realizations from their lived experiences. It is encouraging to learn that the Philippine government has devised methods for applying arbitrary punishment to inmates, even in the face of pervasive dehumanization of those who commit crimes. The PDLs' lived experiences at Penal Farm and Iwahig Prison demonstrate that even those who have committed horrible crimes have a right to a normal life as long as it is one that is governed by laws and regulations to promote self-realization and personal development. How they were treated and valued inside the correctional make them feel that they are worthy of another chance to prove that they can change.

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